

Evaluation Use Of Distance Learning In Jordanian Universities During The COVID19 Pandemic

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 03, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: September 06, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Evaluation; Higher Education Institutions; Distance Learning; COVID19.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13713035</p>	<p><i>Various countries have shifted from face-to-face learning to distance learning in response to the challenges imposed by the spread of the COVID19. Worldwide distance learning has become a global phenomenon. The current study aims to evaluate the use of distance learning in Jordanian universities during the covid19 pandemic. The study has developed standards for using distance learning in Jordanian universities and the current status of using distance learning in Jordanian universities. To achieve these aims, the descriptive approach is adopted. A list of the necessary standards for using distance learning is developed, and the current status of using distance learning in Jordanian universities is determined through five domains, and descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were calculated as well. The results show the weakness of the technological and human infrastructure necessary for distance learning, and its low ability to create an attractive educational environment, making the use of technology a formal matter that does not achieve the slightest added value to the educational process, along with the weak evaluation of the quality of electronic content. Therefore, the study recommends the necessity of providing modern technological and human infrastructure for higher education institutions to activate them neatly to support the continuity of the educational process.</i></p>

Introduction

The whole world communities today face COVID-19 which is a pandemic crisis affecting all aspects of human life. COVID-19 is described by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a global pandemic that invades space and time, attacks societies in their essence, and causes economic, social, financial, and political crises in today's world (Rieley, J. B, 2020). COVID-19 also causes the closure and lockdown of most educational institutions in the world to find options to deal with this challenging situation to reduce the rate of transmission and occurrence of infection and disease (Anderson et al., 2020). Besides, COVID-19 is first recognized in November 2019 in Wuhan City, China, and has since spread globally resulting in the current 2019-2020 coronavirus pandemic (Hui, et al., 2020). Infection of COVID-19 causes severe acute respiratory syndrome virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) (Wenham et al.2020) and it spreads through sneezing, coughing, or talking and can live for long hours on many surfaces, so the World Health Organization has called it the global pandemic (Dun & Bradstree, 2020).

Developing countries are at a low level of competence and preparedness towards the orientation of distance learning, which leads to concern about the issue of education even before the COVID-19 pandemic. At the individual and collective situation and level, students and faculty members face many challenges and obstacles that limit distance learning (Thurman, A. (2019). However, Rani Molla (2020) asserts that the problem lies in the lack of infrastructure necessary for distance learning, requiring the elements of the educational process to use the available facilities, which reduces the opportunities for effective distance learning. Distance learning requires the provision of learning platforms that shall be continuously evaluated to achieve educational outcomes through multimedia, which requires the availability of a good internet connection (Basilaia et al., 2020).

1. Statement of the problem

Without prior warning, higher education institutions in Jordan found themselves in a race against time to shift to a distance learning model imposed by the current circumstances as a result of the COVID19. These institutions have initially responded disproportionately and satisfactorily to this challenge, but the need has become urgent to reconsider the evaluation of distance learning to ensure its quality in facing challenges and contributing to improving the quality of higher education in Jordan. In light of this, the problem of the study emerging from the researcher's work and practice of distance learning and during the second semester of the academic year 2019/2020 A preliminary analysis of the emergent learning process outcomes shows that there are many problems related to distance learning including the weak homogeneity and disparity in student satisfaction levels with distance learning, the low academic follow-up, and the slow Internet connection.

Importantly, the recommendations of recent studies, (Mundy & Hares, 2020), as well as the ten recommendations referred to by the UNESCO report that closing educational institutions harm millions of students in around the world (UNESCO. 2020). Andreas, Nusrat, and Goldin (2020) reported that this virus in most cases remains for a longer period than expected and must be coexisting with it and confirm the necessity that the virus shall not hinder the progress of the education process. Thus, the process of using distance learning shall be evaluated on an ongoing basis.

3. Questions of the study

In light of the problem of the study, the following questions are formatted.

1. What are the standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions?
2. What is the reality of using distance learning in Higher education institutions?

4. Objectives of the study

The current study aims to evaluate the use of distance learning in higher education in Jordan in light of the global spread of the COVID19 pandemic. The study will define the standards for using distance learning in higher education institutions through identifying the standards for using distance learning in higher education and the reality of using distance learning.

5. The Significance of the study

In light of the originality and novelty of the problem addressed in the study, the significance of this study appears in theoretical and practical aspects. The theoretical aspect shows that the study seeks to evaluate the use of distance learning in higher education in Jordan in light of the global spread of the COVID19, which provides an important indicator for examining the first experience in higher education through distance learning. Also, it is the first study in the Jordanian educational environment addressing this key topic due to the novelty of this experience, as the COVID19 pandemic surprises countries and imposes challenges on them without previous notice or announcement. From the practical side, this research is recognized in giving feedback to decision-makers in higher education institutions in deciding on the appropriateness of using distance learning in Higher education institutions and working to identify strengths to strengthen them and identify weaknesses so that a novel plan can be developed to improve the distance learning process and thus provide the recommendations based on the results of the study.

6. Theoretical framework

Social distancing is regarded as the main tool and base necessary for the individual's survival skills. The social development of the learner is negatively affected by the lack of communication and interaction among students and community members. As a result of the spread of the COVID19, distance learning has replaced traditional learning (O'Sullivan, 2017, Krewer, & Frank). Researchers (Essaid El Bachari et al., (2011) believe that distance learning is effective for all and considers the characteristics and needs of learners. Also, Hannay and Newvine (2006) confirm that distance learning provides an opportunity for learning throughout time and anywhere. Visande (2014) indicates that through distance learning, learning outcomes are achieved to a high extent and the impact of learning outcomes remains for a longer period of time because it provides scientific content in more than one way and style.

Distance learning improves the educational practices of the learners, as the study (Tran, Trung; Hoang, Anh-Duc, 2020) proved that it puts a future vision on how to advance learning and achieve sustainable development 4 (SDG4). Likewise, Rao (2011) confirms that distance learning has become a global phenomenon, tremendously contributing to the development of education.

Due to the significance of distance learning, numerous studies are conducted, including a study by Basilaia & Kvavadze (2020), which investigated the level of schools' capabilities to continue the educational process in distance learning after the COVID19 pandemic through Microsoft Teams, where the case study used is 950-school students in Georgia. The results confirmed the success of the rapid transition to distance learning. However, traditional learning remains more effective as the current educational curricula are not designed for distance learning. Another study by Fojtik, (2018) investigated the effectiveness of distance learning compared to traditional learning in the Czech Republic, and the study showed statistically significant differences among students due to the type of learning in favor of traditional learning versus distance learning due to the low preparedness of technological infrastructure in educational institutions.

In light of the previous review, it appears that distance learning faces problems related to digital content, the infrastructure, and the competencies of teachers to implement this type of learning along with the economic cost, especially in developing countries. The current study is a vital addition to previous studies in evaluating the use of distance learning in higher education and the extent of the application of quality standards on it. Distance learning needs pre-preparation and qualification for the educational staff and in this context. McPhee, (2012) indicates that this type of learning requires the preparation of high-quality educational materials, and students need to follow their learning process in an organized and continuous manner, but the majority of students follow it at the end of the semester, which will be reflected in their academic performance. Therefore,

some studies emphasize technical qualification and training of teachers including the study by Klimova (2015) that confirms that the basic problem of distance learning lies in the availability of sufficient and adequate technical expertise for both parties to the learning process. Importantly, distance learning enhances the learner's feeling about learning and education, and also makes him/her feel equal learning opportunities. Warrier (2006) maintains that one of the most important justifications for distance learning is that distance learning breaks the barriers of fear and anxiety among students, and enables the learner to express his opinion as the learner finds it easy to access the teacher even outside the official working hours.

7. Limitations of the study

This study is limited to evaluate the use of distance learning in universities in Jordan in light of the global spread of the COVID19 pandemic. It is also limited to a random sample of public universities in Jordan. Moreover, it is applied in the academic year 2019/2020.

7. Methodology of the study

In light of the objectives and nature of the study, the descriptive approach is used as it is the appropriate scientific approach to the problem of the study, its objectives, and its conclusions.

- **Population and sample study**

The population and sample study composed of all faculty members of the Faculties of Education in three universities in Jordan (Yarmouk University, University of Jordan, and the Middle East University). A simple random sample was selected by the method of (cards/lottery), so the study sample consists of (3) universities, and included (65) faculty members from the Faculties of Education. Table (1) shows the names of the universities of the study sample and the number of faculty members at the Faculty of Education for each university.

Table 1. The names of the universities of the study sample and the number of faculty members

<i>No. Item</i>	<i>Name of University</i>	<i>Number of Faculty Members.</i>
1	Yarmouk University	25
2	University of Jordan	25
3	Middle East University	15
	Total	65

- **Instruments**

The study used to instruments, The first instrument is a list of standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions. Its purpose is to define the standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions. The instrument's reliability is calculated using an internal consistency method using Cronbach's alpha equation, which is (82.9).

The second was a five points Likert-style survey that is developed to determine the use of distance learning during the COVID19 pandemic in higher education institutions. The scale ranging from (1) Strongly Agree to (5) Strongly Disagree.

8. Results

This section presents the results and the answers to the two questions of the study.

First: Answer to the first question "What are the standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions?"

To answer the first question, a list of standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions is prepared. Table (3) shows a matrix for the final list of standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions.

Table 3. Matrix of the list of the standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions

<i>Domains</i>	<i>Standards</i>	<i>Reference Numbers</i>	<i>Indicators</i>
First Domain: Technological Structure	1- The university is characterized by a technological infrastructure suitable for the distance learning system.	2	5
	2- The university provides mechanisms for transforming electronic content to learners.	2	7
	3- The university has technical and technological support for distance learning.	2	4
	4- The university is keen to strengthen the	2	7

	technological infrastructure.		
Second Domain: Electronic Content	1- The university takes into account the relevance of the educational content to the students' developmental characteristics.	2	6
	2- The university designs distance learning resources.	3	6
	3- The university produces distance learning resources.	2	6
	4- The university evaluates the quality of electronic content within the distance learning system.	2	7
	5- The university publishes the electronic system, and uses it in the educational process.	2	6
Third Domain: Faculty Member	1- The faculty member determines the students' needs in distance learning.	2	5
	2- The faculty member designs distance learning strategies and activities.	2	7
	3- The faculty member creates an appropriate electronic environment that takes into account the intended learning outcomes.	2	4
	4- The faculty member is keen on having professional development programs for the distance learning system.	2	8
	5- The faculty member carries out self-evaluation and feedback in the distance learning system.	2	6
	6- The faculty member abides by distance learning controls.	2	8
Fourth Domain: Learner	1 - The learner has the skills to interact with distance learning.	2	8
	2- The learner is proficient in using information and communication technology for the distance learning system.	2	5
	3- The learner shall abide by the controls of using the distance learning system.	2	4
Fifth Domain: Evaluation	1- The university takes into account the foundations of evaluating the elements of the distance learning system.	2	7
	2- The university provides procedures for evaluating the distance learning system.	3	15
Total	20	42	129

Thus, the first question of the study's questions is answered, which reads "What are the standards for using distance learning in Higher education institutions?"

Second: Answer to the second question "What is the reality of using distance learning in Higher education institutions?"

To answer the second question, the study sample and the arithmetic means, and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample individuals are calculated, and they are arranged in descending order according to the arithmetic means of the indicators for each domain, as shown in Table (4).

First Domain: Technological Structure

Table 4. The means and standards deviation of the study sample responses on the first domain: the technological structure (indicators 1: 23).

NO.	INDICATOR	M	SD	DEGREE OF AVAILABILITY OF THE INDICATOR
1	1-3-1-1 The educational university has qualified human resources to pursue the technological infrastructure.	2.95	229.	MEDIUM
2	1-1-1-2 The university is linked to the video conference network of the Directorate for the use of distance learning.	2.69	635.	MEDIUM
3	1-1-2-1 The university has laboratories equipped with modern computers.	2.62	593.	MEDIUM
4	1-1-1-1 The university has equipment and systems for virtual classes.	2.60	596.	LOW
5	1-2-1-4 The university has a website.	2.49	573.	LOW
6	1-3-1-2 The university provides teacher training programs on the distance learning system.	2.42	567.	LOW
7	1-2-2-1 The university determines the mechanisms for documenting electronic content.	2.38	490.	LOW
8	1-1-2-2 The university provides the necessary internet service for distance learning and education.	2.25	775.	LOW
9	1-3-2-2 The university sets a periodic plan for maintaining the technological infrastructure.	2.18	547.	LOW
10	1-3-2-1 The university provides the necessary technical support for networks and computers.	2.11	567.	LOW
11	1-2-2-2 The university controls the management of all distance learning processes.	2.09	482.	LOW
12	1-2-1-3 The university uses software that supports the use of various styles of distance learning.	2.07	539.	LOW
13	1-4-2-3 The university takes into account the needs of students and the privacy of society and its values when applying the experiences of the corresponding institutions.	2.05	524.	LOW
14	1-4-1-4 The university provides courses to train faculty members to use modern technology.	2.04	576.	LOW
15	1-2-1-2 The university determines, through its website, how to receive students.	2.04	508.	LOW
16	1-4-1-1 The university is preparing a plan to update the technological infrastructure for distance learning.	2.02	304.	LOW
17	1-2-1-1 The educational institution publishes electronic courses through its website.	2.00	770.	LOW
18	1-4-2-1 The university sets a plan for cooperation with counterpart institutions in distance learning processes.	1.96	356.	LOW
19	1-2-2-3 The university modifies the procedures of distance learning management processes in light of the evaluation results.	1.95	356.	LOW
20	1-1-2-3 The university commits to a plan to operate laboratories according to distance learning programs.	1.95	621.	LOW
21	1-4-2-2 The university benefits from cooperation with counterpart institutions in distance learning operations.	1.93	424.	LOW
22	1-4-1-3 The university adheres to a teacher training plan.	1.93	424.	LOW
23	2- The university provides funding sources for modernizing the technological infrastructure for distance learning.	1.87	640.	LOW

The results of Table (4) indicate the existence of qualified human resources and their suitability for teaching and distance learning, the link of the educational institution to the video network, and the availability of equipment and systems for virtual classes at the university are of a medium degree. The scores' mean of the sample members ranges between (2.95) and (2.65), while the indicators' score is in the ranking from (4:23) (weak) where their mean is between (2.60) and (1.87).

Second Domain: Electronic Content

Table5.The means and standard deviations of the study sample responses on the second domain: electronic content (indicators 24:54).

NO.	INDICATOR TEXT	AM	SD	DEGREE OF AVAILABILITY OF THE INDICATOR
24	2-1-1-3 The educational designer is committed to the developmental characteristics of learners when determining educational content.	2.69	466.	Medium
25	2-1-2-2 The university takes into account the intended learning outcomes in the electronic content.	2.16	462.	Weak
26	2-2-2-2 The university proposes electronic content activities appropriate to the targeted learning outcomes.	2.09	482.	Weak
27	2-1-1-1 The university determines the developmental characteristics of students.	2.09	617.	Weak
28	2-4-2-4 The university provides feedback on the processes of measuring student achievement rates.	2.07	378.	Weak
29	2-5-1-2 The university works to secure the information of the faculty member within the distance learning system.	2.05	405.	Weak
30	2-3-2-2-2 The university uses various methods of interaction between the elements of the distance learning system.	2.04	383.	Weak
31	1-2-1-2-2 The university analyzes educational problems in light of the current situation.	2.04	331.	Weak
32	2-5-1-1 The university is interested in spreading the education and distance learning system to those concerned.	2.00	272	Weak
33	2-4-2-3 The university prepares various mechanisms for measuring student achievement rates.	2.00	272.	Weak
34	2-4-1-3 The electronic content has basic attractive elements such as (video, animation)	2.00	272.	Weak
35	2-4-2-1 The university links all parts of the electronic content with multiple links.	1.98	304.	Weak
36	2-1-1-2 The university takes into account the needs and interests of students when determining the electronic content.	1.96	508.	Weak
37	2-4-1-1 The university uses electronic content that is constantly updated.	1.95	356.	Weak
38	2-2-2-1 The university determines the multimedia necessary for the distance learning system.	1.95	448.	Weak
39	2-3-1-3 The university carries out periodic follow-up and evaluation of the electronic content production process.	1.93	466.	Weak
40	1-2-1-1 The university determines the appropriate electronic educational content for learners.	1.91	442.	Weak
41	2-1-2-2 The university takes into account the needs of students in light of the results of the analysis of educational problems.	1.91	554.	Weak

42	2-4-2-2 The university defines the activities that the learner will perform.	1.84	462.	Weak
43	1-2-3-2 The university sets clear procedural plans for implementing electronic content.	1.84	501.	Weak
44	2-3-1-1 The university defines clear procedures for producing distance learning system resources.	1.76	508.	Very weak
45	2-1-2-3 The university provides the necessary resources for the distance learning system.	1.71	533.	Very weak
46	2-5-1-3 The university takes into account the intellectual property rights of the distance learning system.	1.64	557.	Very weak
47	2-4-1-2 The university adheres to the standard standards for the production of electronic content.	1.60	564.	Very weak
48	2-3-2-2 The university provides various links that allow connection to the content.	1.56	631.	Very weak
49	2-3-1-2 The university sets a procedural plan to implement the e-content production strategy.	1.56	631.	Very weak
50	2-5-2-2 The university prepares programs to train human resources to follow the quality of distance learning.	1.49	573.	Very weak
51	2-5-2-1 The university sets a plan for monitoring the quality of performance in distance learning.	1.44	601.	Very weak
52	2 2-5-2-3 The university verifies the validity of the distance learning content system links.	1.38	593.	Very weak
53	2-3-2-1 The university defines various tools for interaction in distance learning.	1.38	561.	Very weak
54	2-3-2-3 The university prepares various communications to suit the students 'circumstances.	1.35	552.	Very weak

The results of Table (5) for the indicator in the ranking (24) indicate that the educational designer's commitment to the developmental characteristics of learners when determining the educational content is of a medium degree, where the scores' mean of the sample members reaches (2.69). However, the indicators' score in the ranking from (54:44) is very weak, where their mean is between (1.76) and (1.35). Therefore, the previous results reveal the weakness of defining the specifications of displaying electronic content appropriate to the developmental characteristics of learners and evaluating the quality of electronic content.

Third Domain: Faculty Member

Table 6. The arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the study sample responses on the third domain: faculty member (indicators 92:55).

No.	Indicator Text	AM	SD	Degree of availability of the indicator
55	3-5-2-2 The faculty member diversifies the types of questions through the learners' feedback.	2.69	466.	Medium
56	3-3-1-2 The faculty member interacts with students in the distance learning environment.	2.56	601.	Weak
57	3-6-1-1 The faculty member motivates students to participate in setting evaluation rules.	2.51	717.	Weak
58	3-4-2-1 The faculty member is fluent in using distance learning tools.	2.33	546.	Weak
59	3-4-2-4 The faculty member takes into account the use of modern search engines in the educational process.	2.29	458.	Weak
60	3-2-2-3 A faculty member encourages students to interact with their colleagues	2.25	517.	Weak

	through the institution's website.				
61	3-5-1-1 The faculty member seeks to seek the opinion of the faculty member regarding his performance.	2.24	508.	Weak	
62	3-4-2-2 The faculty member can manage learning resources in the distance learning system.	2.24	429.	Weak	
63	3-4-2-5 The faculty member knows multiple educational sites related to educational content.	2.22	498.	Weak	
64	3-5-1-2 The faculty member documents the students' opinions in it through an appropriate opinion questionnaire.	2.20	404.	Weak	
65	3-4-1-2 The faculty member follows up development programs in using technology in education.	2.16	462.	Weak	
66	3-2-2-2 The faculty member publishes the educational activities on the Internet.	2.16	536.	Weak	
67	3-5-1-3 The faculty member adjusts his educational performance according to the results of the students' opinions analysis.	2.15	524.	Weak	
68	3-4-1-3 The faculty member participates in training programs related to e-learning systems.	2.15	488.	Weak	
69	3-6-2-1 The faculty member avoids using any means indicating discrimination between students	2.11	416.	Weak	
70	3-2-2-1 The faculty member encourages students to communicate within the distance learning system.	2.11	497.	Weak	
71	3-5-2-1 The faculty member provides feedback to learners in the distance learning system.	2.09	398.	Weak	
72	3-4-2-3 The faculty member uses the educational sites in the educational process.	2.04	508.	Weak	
73	3-1-2-1 The faculty member follows up on the learner's performance in the distance learning system.	2.04	331.	Weak	
74	3-6-1-4 The faculty member explains the legal aspects of the distance learning system.	2.00	430.	Weak	
75	3-2-2-1 The faculty member devises various activities that develop students' thinking skills.	2.00	544.	Weak	
76	3-6-2-2 The faculty member is able to efficiently manage the interaction between students.	1.98	451.	Weak	
77	3-6-1-3 The faculty member and students shall be involved in setting the rules for dealing between them.	1.98	304.	Weak	
78	2-3-2-2 The faculty member is keen to follow up the interactive communication between students.	1.98	561.	Weak	
79	3-1-1-2 The faculty member takes into account the developmental characteristics of the learner.	1.96	383.	Weak	
80	3-6-2-4 The faculty member is keen to respect students' privacy.	1.95	229.	Weak	
81	3-3-1-1 The faculty member provides interactive communications in the distance learning environment.	1.91	554.	Weak	

82	3-2-1-3 The faculty member plans to practically use distance learning strategies.	1.89	416.	Weak
83	3-1-2-2 The faculty member identifies students' problems.	1.82	547.	Weak
84	3-5-2-3 The faculty member benefits from the feedback regarding the course.	1.76	576.	Very week
85	3-2-1-4 The faculty member follows up on students 'use of distance learning strategies.	1.67	771.	Very week
86	3-2-1-1 The faculty member selects the appropriate strategies for learning.	1.65	552.	Very week
87	3-4-1-1 The faculty member evaluates his performance periodically.	1.64	677.	Very week
88	3-1-1-1 The faculty member suggests requirements for achieving the educational process objectives.	1.58	567.	Very week
89	3-6-1-2 The faculty member determines the interaction behaviors within the distance learning system.	1.55	633.	Very week
90	3-2-1-2 The faculty member determines the special work rules within the distance learning system.	1.51	573.	Very week
91	3-6-2-3 A faculty member gives students the opportunity to express their views in a democratic atmosphere.	1.42	599.	Very week
92	3-1-2-3 A faculty member suggests solutions to students' problems	1.24	508.	Very week

The results of Table (6) indicate that the responses' mean of the respondents to the indicators is weak, with a mean of between (2.56) and (1.82). The results reflect a weakness in the knowledge and skills necessary to use distance learning in the educational process.

Fourth Domain: Learner

Table 7. The arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the study sample responses on the fourth domain: the learner (indicators 107: 93).

No.	Indicator Text	AM	SD	Degree of availability of the indicator
93	4-1-1-4 The learner uses the evaluation tools of the distance learning system.	2.44	660.	Weak
94	4-1-1-2 The learner identifies the characteristics of the technological research tools associated with distance learning.	2.31	540.	Weak
95	4-3-2-2 The learner differentiates between the pros and cons of communication in the distance learning system.	2.29	762.	Weak
96	4-2-1-3 The learner uses research skills in the distance learning system.	2.25	517.	Weak
97	4-2-2-1 The learner verifies the accuracy of the information obtained.	2.22	498.	Weak
98	4-2-2-2 The learner uses the information obtained in the learning process.	2.16	462.	Weak
99	4-3-1-1 The learner knows the intellectual property laws.	2.07	378.	Weak
100	4-3-1-2 The learner shall abide by the intellectual property laws related to the distance learning system.	1.98	360.	Weak
101	4-2-1-1 The learner knows the technological research tools.	1.96	508.	Weak
102	4-1-2-1 The learner uses various tools in interacting with the faculty member.	1.96	576.	Weak

103	4-3-2-1 The learner adheres to the rules of ethical behavior.	1.95	488.	Weak
104	4-1-1-3 The learner can use the distance learning system operating programs.	1.89	497.	Weak
105	4-1-1-2 The learner defines the characteristics of distance learning.	1.89	416.	Weak
106	4-1-2-2 The learner exchanges content with students.	1.60	710.	Very weak
107	4-1-1-1 The learner knows the basic terminology of the distance learning system.	1.42	599.	Very weak

The results of Table (7) indicate a weakness in the learner's ability to interact with the distance learning system and use the information and communication technology of the distance learning system, as the response's mean of the sample members ranges between (2.44) and (1.89). Also, the indicator's score is ranked (106) and regarded as very weak, with a mean of (1.60), and the indicator's score is (107) which is considered very weak with a mean of (1.42).

Fifth Domain: Evaluation

Table 8. The arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the study sample responses on the fifth domain: evaluation (indicators 129: 108).

No.	Indicator Text	AM	SD	Degree of availability of the indicator
108	5-2-2-3 The results of the evaluation will appear for students (talented, outstanding, and weak).	2.69	466.	Medium
109	5-2-3-4 The university prepares a feedback on the evaluation processes.	2.56	570.	Weak
110	5-2-1-7 The evaluation process is continuous.	2.55	571.	Weak
111	5-1-1-1 The university is committed to evaluating all processes of the e-learning system.	2.33	771.	Weak
112	5.2.1.6 The evaluation process is objective.	2.33	840.	Weak
113	5-2-1-5 The university provides assessment tools for learners.	2.25	517.	Weak
114	5-2-1-1 The institution shall set specific standards for evaluation.	2.16	501.	Weak
115	5-2-2-1 The university provides data on evaluation processes.	2.15	448.	Weak
116	5-1-1-2 The university shall involve all stakeholders in the evaluation process.	2.04	543.	Weak
117	5-1-2-4 The university announces the evaluation results to the concerned parties (students - parents).	2.00	509.	Weak
118	5-2-3-1 The university sets up mechanisms to follow up the evaluation.	1.98	913.	Weak
119	5-1-2-3 The university is keen to document the evaluation processes.	1.96	543.	Weak
120	5-2-3-3 The university evaluation process.	1.91	398.	Weak
121	5-1-2-1 The university sets standards for evaluation processes.	1.91	586.	Weak
122	5-2-1-2 The university verifies the validity of the evaluation tools.	1.85	524.	Weak
123	5-2-1.8 The evaluation process includes the targeted learning outcomes.	1.82	796.	Weak
124	5-1-1-3 The university determines the mechanisms for implementing evaluation processes for the distance learning system.	1.80	487.	Very weak
125	5-1-1-1 The university is committed to	1.80	558.	Very weak

	evaluate all distance learning system operations.				
126	5-2-1-3 The university checks the stability of the evaluation tools.	1.71	685.	Very weak	
127	5-2-2-2 The university handles evaluation process data statistically.	1.47	573.	Very weak	
128	5-1-2-2 The evaluation process is transparent.	1.45	603.	Very weak	
129	5-2-3-2 The university provides improvement programs and plans for learners in light of the evaluation results	1.36	557.	Very weak	

The results of Table (8) for the indicator specified in the ranking (108) that the evaluation results for students (talented, outstanding, weak) are shown with a medium degree, where the response's mean of the sample members are (2.69). However, the results for the indicators specified in the ranking (109:123) to the university's weak provision of appropriate evaluation tools for the education and e-learning system that enables it to identify strengths for strengthening and identifying weaknesses to develop proposals for improvement. Thus, the second question of the study, which reads "What is the reality of using distance learning in Higher education institutions?", is answered.

Discussion

The previous results in the first and second domains illustrate the weakness of the technological infrastructure necessary to transfer the electronic content to learners, the weakness of adequate technical support, the lack of mechanisms to support the technological infrastructure, and the lack of modernization. Precisely, this is due to the lack of qualified human resources to follow the technological infrastructure equipment in higher education institutions, the educational designer's lack of commitment to the developmental characteristics of learners when determining the educational content, the lack of a clear definition of the specifications of the electronic content display appropriate to the developmental characteristics of learners, and the lack of production of distance learning system resources. Notably, the results of the current study are in agreement with the results of the study (Fojtik, 2018), which confirms the existence of deficiencies in the design of software and multi-educational media necessary for distance learning. It is also in line with the study (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020), which confirms the lack of providing electronic courses and basic electronic content elements necessary to implement distance learning. Accurately, the results in the third domain are due to the scarcity of the faculty member's identification of students' needs in the distance learning system, the lack of design by the faculty member of the strategies and activities of the distance learning system, and the lack of faculty members preparing an appropriate electronic environment that takes into account the targeted learning outcomes. The study's results are consistent with the study (Rashidi, 2020), which confirms the absence of a clear and specific role for a faculty member in distance learning, and a deficiency in providing the necessary software to prepare electronic lessons and tests.

Besides, the results in the fourth and fifth domain are due to the lack of interest of the faculty member in developing these skills among students and evaluating them, the poor knowledge of the learner in the regulations of using the distance learning system, and the weakness of providing appropriate evaluation tools for the distance learning system. The results of the study agree with (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020) and the study (KLimova, 2015), which confirm weak students' skills in using educational websites on the Internet, poor communication with faculty members through e-mail. Also, the study (Vimbi, 2018) indicates that programs based on distance learning may be difficult to implement in laboratory sciences and scientific colleges and the weakness of the faculty member's ability to conduct electronic tests.

Recommendation

In light of the study's procedures, statement of the problem, and its findings, the study recommends applying the distance learning use's standards to improve their use in university learning, developing faculty members to integrate technology in education to select the distance learning and take advantage of educational and e-learning resources available on the Internet, and paying attention to the infrastructure of higher education institutions to provide them with modern computer laboratories connected to the Internet.

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